

Influence of flag leaf area on rice seed germinability and vigor

C. P. Thiagarajan, Seed Technology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We studied the relationship between flag leaf area and panicle size, panicle weight, 1,000-grain weight, germination, and vigor in short-duration ADT36, TKM9, and IR50 rices. Flag leaf areas were 10.50-26.72 cm² in ADT36, 11.61-33.75 cm² in TKM9, and 6.50-19.95 cm² in IR50.

The results indicate a close relationship between flag leaf area and yield and quality parameters (see table).

In ADT36, correlations between flag leaf area for all parameters were

Correlations between flag leaf area and yield and quality parameters of 3 short-duration rices. Tamil Nadu, India, 1989.

Variety	Leaf area (cm)	Panicle size	Panicle weight	1,000-grain weight	Germination	Vigor index
ADT36		0.9184**	0.9150**	0.8220**	0.7120**	0.6365**
TKM9	11.61-28.75	0.9634**	0.8916**	-0.4236*	0.4559*	0.5122*
	>28.75	-0.8434**	-0.3889	—	-0.6807**	-0.8036**
IR50	6.50-14.30	0.8718**	0.9066**	0.9631**	0.6142**	0.9485**
	>14.30	-0.9224**	0.8550**	-0.7910**		

positive and highly significant. In TKM9, the correlations for all parameters except 1,000-grain weight were positive and significant for flag leaf areas 11.61-28.75 cm²; large flag leaf areas showed significantly negative correlations. In the case of 1,000-grain weight in TKM9 there was a significant correlation with leaf areas 11.61-28.75 cm²; thereafter the correlation was not significant.

In IR50, the correlations between flag leaf area and panicle weight, germination, and vigor index were positive and significant. For flag leaf areas 6.50-14.30 cm², the correlations with panicle size and 1,000-grain weight were positive and significant; leaf areas 15.65-19.95 cm² had negative correlations. □

Heterosis and heterobeltiosis for five morphoanatomical characters of rice panicle

S. Mallik, A. M. Aguilar, and B. S. Vergara, Plant Physiology Department, IRRI

We studied five morphoanatomical characters of the rice panicle in 34 parents and their 43 progeny hybrids. The characters were inner vascular bundle (IVB) and outer vascular bundle (OVB) just below the neck node, culm diameter (CD), medullary cavity diameter (MC), and culm thickness (CT). The number of vascular bundles is correlated positively with the number of primary branches (where heavier grains are located). Higher numbers of vascular bundles possibly indicate a better transport system.

Parents consisted of 9 IR varieties and lines, 10 other indicas, 5 *glaberrima* accessions, and 10 upland lines derived from an anther-cultured Moroberekan/Palawan cross.

Parents and their hybrids were grown in the field and greenhouse during 1988 dry season. Data from 10 primary tillers of each parent and

hybrid were recorded when panicles emerged completely from the flag leaf sheath.

Numbers of IVB and OVB were almost the same in IR and indica varieties; numbers of OVB were higher in *glaberrima* and upland lines. OVB/IVB ratios varied from 1.3 to 1.7 in *glaberrima* and upland rices; ratios were almost 1.0 in IR varieties.

Estimates of overall degree and direction of heterosis (F₁-P) were significant and positive for IVB (1.36**) and OVB (0.67*), indicating dominance of higher values. Estimates for CD (0.05), MC (0.09), and CT (-0.02) were not significant.

Values for individual F₁ families differed from overall estimates for heterosis in IVB and OVB (see figure).

Heterosis (H) and heterobeltiosis (Hb) for inner vascular bundle (IVB) and outer vascular bundle (OVB) in 43 crosses. IRRI, 1988 dry season.